

LandSense

A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Deliverable 4.8

Feedback and Evaluation of LandSense Demonstration Cases

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Feedback and Evaluation of LandSense Demonstration Cases
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Short Description:
This deliverable provides an overview of the demonstration cases, summarizing the feedback from each one and evaluating them based on a set of criteria, which is used to reflect on each case. Recommendations are then provided based on the experiences from the demonstration cases.
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Executive summary

The LandSense Citizen Observatory offers a wide breadth of citizen science and crowdsourcing approaches to address key questions within the domain of land use and land cover monitoring. Some of the LandSense pilots focused on in-situ observations using mobile apps, whereas other pilots were centered around satellite-image interpretations during dedicated mapathons. The design and implementation of the seven demonstration pilots across seven countries covering the urban, agriculture and forest habitat domains led to key discoveries and lessons learned by the consortium. We share stakeholder and volunteer feedback and provide a self-evaluation of all demonstration pilots, while addressing sustainability and further exploitation potential.

1 Introduction

This deliverable provides an overview of the LandSense demonstration cases in the urban, agriculture and forest habitat domains, each of which is described in more details in deliverables D4.5 ([Demo 1: Cost reduction and data conflation in monitoring land change II](#)), D4.6 ([Demo 2: Monitoring agricultural land use and provision of value-added agricultural services II](#)) and D4.7 ([Demo 3: Forest and habitat monitoring using innovative technologies II](#)). Each case is described, followed by a summary of the generic feedback gathered from experiences with running each case and an evaluation. The evaluation is based on the following criteria:

- Number of users engaged
- Number of downloads of the app;
- Number of observations collected;
- Uptake of the solution by local authorities, organizations, incorporation into business solutions; and
- Other impacts.

Although other LandSense KPIs were formulated to monitor and evaluate the LandSense project as a whole (available in the third Period Technical Report), these aforementioned measures, in particular, represent a way to reflect on the performance of each demonstration case. This is followed by recommendations arising from this evaluation for future citizen observatories on land use and land cover (LULC).

2 Urban Landscape Dynamics

2.1 City of Vienna

Objective: Complement local administration urban planning processes by gaining insights and data from citizens about the usage and perceptions of urban green and open spaces.

Tool: [City Oases mobile app](#) (previously known as Frei.Raum.Netz), publicly available since March 2019.

Lead: UBA

Key Stakeholders: City of Vienna (urban development and urban planning department – MA18), Vienna University of Technology, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences

Data: open access data from the CityOases campaign is available [here](#)

Within LandSense we developed City Oases, a mobile application, that aims not only to stimulate civic engagement to monitor changes within the urban environment, but also to enable users to drive improvements by providing city planners with information about the public perception of urban spaces. A demonstration pilot of City Oases was launched in March 2019 for the city of Vienna. Due to COVID-19, we were not able to run an additional campaign in 2020, which would have built on the experiences gained in 2019 and led to further data collection.

The app is centered on finding and evaluating ‘City Oases’ – the ideal places to hang out in an urban environment. Where are the best places for a romantic date? Where can you skate? Where is it cool on a hot summer’s day? Open urban spaces can be used in many ways. Users can search for specific activities, visit one of the points indicated on the map and then evaluate this point. For example, if you pick an activity in the CityOases app, we then show the locations on a map where you can do them, including the rating of previous users and pictures from that location. If you visit that location, you can rate it based on a few selected subjective criteria. If you know of an interesting location that is openly accessible, but it is not yet marked on the map, then it can be added along with a list of activities and photographs. The picture module within the application encourages you to take photos in the four cardinal directions. Additionally, you can input your perceptions including whether it is noisy, clean or if the infrastructure is attractive. Different themes, such as adaptation to a changing urban climate throughout a year, can be quantified within a campaign. For example, in the summer of 2019 during a heatwave, ZAMG provided maps of thermal comfort to indicate areas with high urban heat islands and cooler locations.

The information from the app has provided the LandSense team – and stakeholders – with information regarding land cover (via the photographs taken) and land use (via activities/subjective feelings), as well as the state and setup of the area over a long period of time. The City Oases app was developed with inputs from a range of stakeholders including the Technical University of Vienna, the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, and the City of Vienna (Magistrate 18 - Urban development and urban planning department – MA18). The app was co-developed by IIASA, UBA and G2K. IIASA was the lead technical developer, UBA led the stakeholder consultations and G2K was responsible for the dissemination and communication.

The app has been designed with up-scaling in mind – ready for multilingual use and with a set of activities and subjective feelings that fits almost every city. While in Vienna, the pre-set quest points focused mainly on those from the Frei.Raum.Netz application and the city parks, providing MA 18 with vital information about the perception of one of the most important development features in the cities, other cities are free to define their own areas of interest.

Feedback on CityOases - Vienna

- In general, there is strong competition vying for the attention of users. Strong and sustained effort is required to attract and retain the attention of a critical mass of volunteers. This is a key challenge that the City Oases team faced. The team reacted by engaging their personal/professional networks as much as possible.
- Based on the feedback from some participants, there was a reluctance to install additional apps due to data restrictions on individual mobile phones.
- Pupils and youth prefer WiFi access rather than using mobile phone data to download apps. The team ensured that at all promotion events, WiFi access was available to overcome this barrier.
- Media coverage of the CityOases app was extensive but perhaps there was some overpromising on the functionality; this led to frustration by some users due to the app performance (i.e lack of initial input data).
- A key challenge on the road to empowerment and e-democracy is to gain a crucial mass of data contributions to draw conclusions for the area/site concerned. As such, a low number of data contributions might lead to misleading results and opinions.
- On a political level, the need to acquire subjective perceptions from citizens is gaining attention, hence apps like City Oases are timely for city administrations (such as MA 18).

Evaluation of City Oases – Vienna

Criteria	Result
Number of users engaged	262
Number of downloads of the app	2,315
Number of observations collected	857 locations visited, 1,332 observations collected, 1500 photographs uploaded
Uptake of the solution by local authorities, organizations, incorporation into business solutions	Due to COVID-19, it was not possible to run a campaign in 2020, which may have provided data that MA18 would find useful. The app is, however, fully available for continued use by the city if desired.
Other impacts	Other cities have expressed an interest in City Oases but funding is a major constraint to scaling this to other cities.

The experiences with the city of Vienna (MA18) were generally positive, but in order to move this app from a demonstration to an operational tool for data collection would require further funding as well as greater ‘ownership’ by the city. It was unfortunate that a further campaign was not possible due to COVID-19, which may have provided more data (and hence evidence of the value of the data for urban planning) as well as the opportunity to continue to improve the app, ironing out any performance issues. On a positive note, there is interest in the City Oases app from other cities but translating this interest into a project with funding is a clear constraint. Nevertheless, the app is available and can be used by other interested parties.

2.2 City of Amsterdam

Objective: Test new methods of obtaining location specific information on subjective perception and preferences for urban green space and assess how this information can inform sustainable urban development.

Tool: [Mijn Park mobile application](#)

Lead: VUA

Key Stakeholders: City of Amsterdam

Data: open access data from the MijnPark campaign is available [here](#)

City-dwellers are realizing the benefits of green spaces and are flocking to urban parks. City planners face the challenge of ensuring that urban green spaces are functional for all citizens. To make informed choices, they need the right information, which is where the LandSense-powered ‘Mijn Park’ (My Park) app can help.

Research shows that when considering the social functions of urban green spaces, quality is just as important as quantity. It is easy enough to map how much green space there is, but how do we measure their quality? How do city planners ensure that the city’s green areas are attractive, accessible and inclusive for everyone? VUA in collaboration with IASA developed Mijn Park, a mobile application to aid city planners to address these questions. As part of the LandSense Citizen Observatory, the Mijn Park app asked respondents to go to several locations in a park and provide subjective responses to those locations. They were then further questioned about how they use the whole park and how much they would like to see certain changes made in the park. A pilot campaign was conducted in the summer of 2018 in Rembrandt park in Amsterdam, and insights from the citizen-driven observations were shared with the Department of Planning and Sustainability of Amsterdam. The pilot was very successful and project managers across the City of Amsterdam have been requesting more information and inquiring whether they can also use the app. Therefore, plans are being made for incorporating lessons learned from the pilot and expanding the use of the app to make it even more useful to informing spatial planning and decision making.

Feedback on MijnPark – Amsterdam

- Results indicate that such approaches led to greater engagement from younger audiences, who are traditionally difficult to reach from an urban planning perspective. In fact, the app appeared to give less biased results compared to traditional survey methods, e.g., answers were provided that covered the full range of possible answers rather than more positive answers is often found in surveys.

- A key challenge is translating the abundance of information received via the app into visualizations and insights that are useful to the relevant decision makers, as well as to the general public. For example, we have worked on a map that shows several results at once for the general public and specific maps that identify key area of interests for the decision makers.
- Respondents from the original campaign, who had given permission for the use of their email, were approached to test the online survey and asked to provide inputs for improvement. Based on these tests, improvements were made to the survey. To date, there have been 200 participants in this new campaign. Areas differed in their response rates – some have over 20% response to the letters while others are as low as 1%.
- Methods to analyse the resulting data in light of densification projects are being developed. An important focus of this data analysis is to develop visualisations and graphics that are easily understood by lay people – the citizens themselves – in order to facilitate feedback and further engagement.

Evaluation of MijnPark – Amsterdam

Criteria	Result
Number of users engaged	154
Number of downloads of the app	796
Number of observations collected	377
Uptake of the solution by local authorities, organizations, incorporation into business solutions	The methodology employed in MijnPark was very well received by the city administration and there is keen interest to apply this approach to other areas in Amsterdam.
Other impacts	VUA is continuing research, refining the approach and scaling up to larger areas of the city to assess the effect of urban densification on subjective green space values. While this project does not use the dedicated app, it builds on the participation method demonstrated in LandSense and will help to refine and improve ways to involve public perception and preferences in informing planning decisions. It is testing new ways of reaching out to and engaging a broader range of participants as well as how to improve information visualization and feedback to those very participants. This campaign is called Mijn Park Amsterdam. The new initiative will also enable decision makers with better insight into the social functions of green spaces and how the trade-offs with development plans can better be assessed to enhance multifunctionality in dense urban environments.

The results from the Amsterdam demonstration case are actually very encouraging, and they represent an upscaling from the original work undertaken with the city of Vienna. Through a flexible response in developing technologies, LandSense was able to meet the needs of this additional demonstration case quite

early on in the project. However, the main result was to raise awareness of the potential of citizen observatories within the city of Amsterdam, who are clearly continuing research with VU on co-designing solutions to gather information from citizens to inform the urban planning processes.

2.3 City of Toulouse and surrounding areas

Objective: Evaluate how contributions from interested experts (i.e. public authorities, engineering students, etc.) can be integrated with the French Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) authoritative database

Tools: [Paysages mobile application](#), [Paysages web application](#) and [LACO-Wiki](#)

Lead: IGN-FRANCE

Key Stakeholders: Urban Planning Agency - Toulouse, Territorial Departmental Direction of Toulouse (31), Regional Direction of IGN (South Wes, Engineering Schools of IGN-France (ENSG), University of Toulouse.

Data: open access data from the Toulouse campaigns are available [here](#)

The French National Mapping Agency (Institut National de l'Information Géographique et Forestière - IGN) is responsible for producing and maintaining the spatial data sets for all of France. At the same time, they must satisfy the needs of different stakeholders who are responsible for decisions at multiple levels from local to national. IGN produces many different maps including detailed road networks and LULC maps over time. The information contained in these maps is crucial for many of the decisions made about urban planning, resource management and landscape restoration as well as other environmental issues in France. Recently, IGN has started the process of creating a high-resolution LULC map, aimed at developing smart and accurate monitoring services of LULC over time. To help update and validate the French LULC database, citizens and interested stakeholders contributed using the Paysages mobile and web applications. This approach presented an opportunity to evaluate the integration of citizens in the IGN process of updating and validating LULC data.

The goal of the Toulouse pilot was to collect information in order to update authoritative LULC data. Contributors carried out the following two tasks:

- **Validated** changes detected by the LandSense Change Detection Service: for each new detected construction (having the types industrial, infrastructure and residential), the contributor should validate the change and the type of construction.
- **Refined the classification** to differentiate between commercial, industrial and residential classes: for each aggregated class US235, choosing a new class based on visual interpretation: industrial (US2), commercial (US3) or residential (US5).

Feedback on Paysages – Toulouse

- Feedback from the contributors/stakeholders was that the validation task was relatively easy whereas the classification task was difficult, given the LULC nomenclature.
- The Paysages application drew keen interest from certain target groups such as IGN partners and GIS and engineering students; however, it was very challenging to attract a broader audience, evidenced from the first campaign in which citizens in Toulouse were targeted.

- The mapathon approach was straightforward to organize and easy to replicate, i.e., armchair mapping, as compared to in-situ campaigns, requiring mobilization of volunteers for field work. Hence the mobile app was not as successful as mapathons organized using both the Paysages web application and the LACO-Wiki software developed by IIASA.
- The mapathon approach facilitates peer-to-peer learning and knowledge exchange about LULC, EO data and other relevant topics.
- Communication was essential for the success of the mapathon approach and to keep students engaged. Immediate feedback was provided just after the mapathons so that users could see the results of their efforts. Once the data were analysed with respect with the contributor agreement and accuracy (see D5.6), the teachers presented the results to the students, which provided a greater awareness of how the data are used but also learning in terms of mistakes made.
- The IGN team involved in the campaign made presentations to the IGN production department and to the local authorities to present the results of the mapathons including the quality assurance and data conflation results. The feedback was positive in terms of demonstrating the potential of citizen contributions to updating the LULC database.

Evaluation of Paysages – Toulouse

Criteria	Result
Number of users engaged	131
Number of downloads of the app	176
Number of observations collected	6500+ observations/validations, 460+ photographs
Uptake of the solution by local authorities, organizations, incorporation into business solutions	IGN is clearly interested in this type of solution, but operationalization will require further investment. However, a recent analysis demonstrating cost reductions in an area of France (beyond Toulouse) have provided additional evidence for the benefits of this approach.
Other impacts	IGN and other local authorities were particularly interested in the Change Detection Service of LandSense. Here they see one of the greatest potentials in identifying dynamic change in the urban landscape although it was only demonstrated for one type of change (i.e., building construction). Further investigation into use and expansion of this service will require further investment.

Much was learned from this demonstration case. The original idea was to involve citizens directly in the collection of LULC data, with six different tasks implemented in the Paysages mobile app. The initial uptake of the app by citizens was, however, poor, which led to a change in direction. First the mobile app was simplified so that only one task was implemented, which was then used in some limited in situ data collection by IGN staff and local stakeholders. The largest change to the approach made was the use of mapathons, which engaged a range of stakeholders in several short events to gather LULC data and validate change from

the LandSense Change Detection Service. This provided a considerable amount of data on which to further demonstrate that the information could be used in a semi-automated way to update IGN’s authoritative LULC database. A recent analysis by IGN has shown that there were no cost reductions in the Toulouse case but when applied to another area, i.e., Nior, a considerable cost reduction can be found. Moving from a demonstration case to operational workflows will require further investment but the key stakeholders in this demonstration case have been convinced of the value and feasibility of this approach. The LandSense Change Detection Service could become a key component of these future workflows as the interest is there, but further investigation into other types of urban change is still required. Hence more investment is needed.

2.4 OSMLanduse

Objective: Demonstrate how citizen-contributed data and Earth Observation (EO) data can update authoritative databases with a strong focus on improving data/map quality

Tools: [OSMLanduse](#) and [LACO-Wiki](#)

Lead: UHEI

Key Stakeholders: City of Heidelberg initially but spatial extent is European

Augmentation and cost reduction of authoritative data through citizen science is a key aspect for LandSense, in particular, to complement authoritative LULC related information. This pilot produced a land use prototype based on the CORINE land cover legend leveraged from OpenStreetMap (OSM) and is available at osmlanduse.org. The land use product was further refined for the LandSense pilot cities of Heidelberg, Toulouse and Vienna. During the course of the project, those sites with increased attention were subsequently extended. In 2018, Geneva was added, where the analysis for Toulouse was refined using very high-resolution data and specific building classifications. Additionally, research was performed to improve the mapping accuracy and further extension of the areas of interest. As a result of our pilot activities, the suitability of land use information provided by OSM was estimated and the most appropriate land use classes were identified, namely: urban residential, industrial, agricultural and forest classes.

The LandSense pilot OSMLanduse collected data through 12 armchair mapathons to validate the osmlanduse.org product through a combination of pixel- and polygon-based validation activities of land use features. Data continue to be gathered through a special mapathon interface set up for the European Week of Cities and Regions, which will continue to improve the OSMLanduse product.

Feedback on OSMLanduse

- Organizations of mapathons, drawing on students from the University of Heidelberg, was straightforward and easy to organize; students were willing to take part.
- Based on the results from the demonstration case, certain OSM land use classes are an appropriate representation of reality and can be used as a reliable land use estimates for authoritative, commercial and operational use.
- There is clear interest in such a product by local authorities, e.g., the Metropolitan Rhine-Neckar (MRN), which is an area that crosses federal state boundaries in Germany. The Geonet organization from the

MRN (funded by both public and commercial organizations) sees the value in such a product because it represents a harmonization of LULC since each federal state has their own maps and workflows in place. Hence Geonet MRN has made a link to osmlanduse.org on its website.

Evaluation of OSMLanduse

Criteria	Result
Number of users engaged	145
Amount of data collected	24,760 observations
Uptake of the solution by local authorities, organizations, incorporation into business solutions	Interest by local authorities has been expressed but OSMLanduse is still under development as largely a research product
Other impacts	Results showed that the osmlanduse.org product is more accurate than CORINE land cover in some regions. In addition, numerous e-mail requests and queries on the implementation of the web mapping service and extraction of OSMLanduse data were received during the course of LandSense, indicating interest in the product.

The OSMLanduse application was developed as part of the LandSense project, building on the expertise the UHEI has with OSM. Much of the emphasis of this demonstration case was on the development of the technology, i.e., using OSM, remote sensing and machine learning to turn OSM into a land use map, and validation using citizens using the LACO-Wiki crowdsourcing platform developed by IIASA. Such a land use product is being extended to Europe and it has many potential applications, particularly in providing up to date information on land use, which can complement authoritative products that are produced less frequently, as well as harmonized products that are of interest to organizations such as Geonet MRN and would be to other metropolitan regional organizations in Germany.

3 Agricultural Land Use

<p>Objective: Leverage the power of EO systems and crowdsourcing techniques to deliver value added service to farmers and farmer associations in Vojvodina, Serbia.</p> <p>Tools: CropSupport mobile application and CropSupport web application</p> <p>Lead: INOSENS</p> <p>Key Stakeholders: Center for organic production Selenca, Farmers' Club Selenca, Association Turinka, Agricultural High Schools, University of Novi Sad</p> <p>Data: open access data from Serbian campaigns are available here</p> <p>Data: open access data from street level imagery are available here</p>
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The LandSense agricultural demonstration pilot has focused on leveraging the power of EO systems and advanced crowdsourcing techniques to deliver value added services to European farmers and public

authorities in the agricultural sector. Pilot activities, led by INOSENS, were localized in Vojvodina province of Serbia and were implemented over two phases. During the Phase 1 campaign (Nov 2017-Sep 2018), agricultural high school students and master students from the University of Novi Sad were actively involved in data collection. During the Phase 2 campaign (Feb-Oct 2019), a group of individual farmers participated in the collection of agricultural in-situ data. The mobile and web-based [CropSupport application](#), developed by INOSENS, was the primary tool for in-situ data collection related to crop type and farm management. Besides the functionalities for intuitive in-situ data collection, the application allows users to access information related to their land free of charge, such as weather forecasts for the micro locations of their parcels, results from the LandSense Change Detection Service as well as processed satellite images that contain information on potential stress of crops due to exposure to pests, plant diseases, water scarcity or nutrient elements in the soil (e.g., NDVI and other vegetation and moisture indexes).

Feedback on Agricultural Monitoring – Vojvodina, Serbia

- Farmers have a very tight time schedule during the growing season so there was not much time for side activities like engagement with CropSupport, which made the process of farmer engagement difficult (in phase II). However, close contact with the farmers (i.e., phone calls, monthly visits) ensured continued engagement. Working with the students studying agronomy in phase I was easier.
- Farmers need adequate motivation to collect in situ data voluntarily, e.g., this would be easier in the framework of compliance.
- Some of the mobile devices of the farmers were old so this affected the performance of the app at times, but users did not specifically raise any issue with the functionality of the mobile or web app.
- There were issues with the Change Detection Service because Serbian farmers own narrow crop parcels with a usual width of 50m so they could not obtain useful data from the service. Hence the Change Detection Service should be applied to wider parcels.

Evaluation of CropSupport – Vojvodina, Serbia

Criteria	Result
Number of users engaged	100+ (25 farmers; more than 75 students)
Number of downloads of the app	100+ on Google Playstore
Number of observations collected	100 fields delineated and 220 photographs
Uptake of the solution by local authorities, organizations, incorporation into business solutions	The CropSupport service is being continued via other H2020 proposals and via the business plan outlined in D6.9.
Other impacts	The JRC sees value in these type of self-reporting applications, particularly with the changes now taking place in the Common Agricultural Policy.

This demonstration case was implemented in two phases. In phase 1, students were mainly targeted while the technology (mobile and web app) was developed. In phase 2, farmers were engaged, and this proved to

be more difficult, due to the time commitments of farmers and issues with older mobile phones. However, the CropSupport service has been tested and shown to work although integration with a compliance framework (such as CAP) would provide greater incentives to be used in the future.

4 Forest and Habitat Monitoring

4.1 Spain

Objective: Monitor the state of Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas (IBAs) and Natura 2000 sites by focusing on the threats that affect various habitats (arid lands, wetlands, grasslands, etc.).

Tool: [Natura Alert mobile and web application](#)

Lead: BLI

Key Stakeholders: Ministry for the Ecological Transition (MITECO): linked to ART12 and ART17 reporting (birds and habitats), Regional authorities (management plans of national parks, reserves, nature parks, etc.), SEO regional offices across Spain, IBA caretakers in Spain

In Spain, there are 469 IBAs and 2,324 Natura 2000 sites (657 SPAs and 1667 SCI/SAC/pSCI). Monitoring the IBA network is a key challenge for SEO/BirdLife due to limited resources to cover this large number of sites. To address this problem, Natura Alert has been developed within the LandSense Citizen Observatory project. The mobile app and web portal allow users to pinpoint the location of threats to biodiversity and habitat changes, to help prevent further damage or loss to our biodiversity. We are particularly interested in threats that are occurring inside IBAs, Key Biodiversity Areas (KBAs) and Natura 2000 sites in the European Union, although submitting records in other areas is also possible. Information on the condition of these sites, the threats to them, the conservation measures in place and the changes in these aspects over time are essential to set priorities, hold governments to account and inform policies and decision makers. Volunteers can share their observations with the wider community and help to map the state of the most valuable sites around the world for birds and biodiversity using the technology developed in the LandSense project.

The Nature Alert mobile and web app were developed as part of the LandSense project, led by IIASA but with significant inputs from BirdLife and Sinergise. Using the Natura Alert mobile app, volunteers can record threats in the field, where the threats are aligned with the IUCN official threat categories. Photographs and videos can also be uploaded to provide further documentation of the threats. The Natura Alert web app can be used to visualize these threats while a country level dashboard allows users to see national summaries. The Natura web app was also designed to fit into the workflow of national IBA coordinators in collating threats submitted by volunteers and producing a threat assessment report per IBA. This information then feeds into the World Biodiversity Database. LandSense was instrumental in improving the workflows of BirdLife in Spain.

Feedback on Natura Alert - Spain

- The consultative process between BLI, IIASA, SEO and Burung was time consuming but the co-design process led to a vastly improved product. A new version has been developed to further facilitate uptake by potential partners in Greece, Netherlands, Tunisia and Argentina.
- The mobile and web application received strong positive feedback from SEO volunteers as it offered an improved and digital workflow compared to current protocols.
- The feedback from external partners was also encouraging as it was determined that there is no current app in the market to monitor threats to IBAs and Natura 2000 sites.

The evaluation of Natura Alert in Spain is provided together with the demonstration case on Flores Island, Indonesia, which is described in the next section.

4.2 Flores Island, Indonesia

Objective: Monitor the state of IBAs/KBAs by focusing on the threats that affect the habitats and the biodiversity for select regions on Flores Island, Indonesia

Tool: [Natura Alert mobile and web application](#)

Lead: BLI

Key Stakeholders: Development Planning Agency at sub-national level (PAPEEDA), Nature Conservation Agency (KSDA), Environmental Agency (BLH), Forest Management Unit (KPH), Forum Komunikasi Kawasan Mbeliling (FPKM), Village & Community Empowerment Agency (DPMD), Village authorities, Local Conservation Group from Mbeliling

In Indonesia, the LandSense project is being implemented in one of the most beautiful landscapes of Flores Island, i.e., the so-called Mbeliling Landscape. This area consists of preserved and community-owned forests. Due to the area's rich biodiversity, it is classified as a Key Biodiversity Area. As the pressure on Mbeliling's forests continues to grow, significant rates of deforestation and forest degradation are occurring. This process is destroying natural habitats, with terrible consequences for forest biodiversity.

For the first time ever in the Eastern part of Indonesia, the LandSense project has helped to build an innovative citizen observatory for forest and habitat monitoring, by connecting local communities with remote sensing and apps. LandSense has allowed communities to play a key role in forest and habitat monitoring by getting them directly involved in the co-creation of the solution. The results of the monitoring have provided valuable inputs to the village development in four targeted villages, promoting demand-driven policy response and raising village agendas to become a development priority.

In addition to using the Natura Alert app for collecting information on threats during field-based campaigns (led by BLI), the Indonesian pilot focused on validating outputs, i.e., alerts generated by the Change Detection Service. Four campaigns took place during 2019 in which the alerts were validated on the ground.

Feedback on Natura Alert - Indonesia

- The consultative process between BLI, IIASA, SEO and Burung was time consuming but the co-design process led to a vastly improved product. A new version has been developed to further facilitate uptake by potential partners in Greece, Netherlands, Tunisia and Argentina
- The face-to-face workshops were a very important way to engage stakeholders and bring them on board.
- Good agreement between the satellite-based changes and the field observations gave volunteers confidence in the LandSense change detection methodology and protocols.
- Social media has been a powerful tool for disseminating stories about the activities and engaging volunteers.

Evaluation of Natura Alert – Spain and Indonesia

Criteria	Result
Number of active users	100+
Number of observations collected	502 threats, 1 video, 204 photographs (Spain) 276 threats, 10 videos, 379 photographs (Flores Island, Indonesia) 88 alerts validated (Flores Island, Indonesia), which were prioritized from the much larger set of alerts generated by the system (1,815 alerts)
Uptake of the solution by local authorities, organizations, incorporation into business solutions	Natura Alert has been identified as an application with significant potential to transform the operational workflow of IBA monitoring not just in Spain but across numerous BLI partners including Greece, the Netherlands and Turkey, among others. The solution will continue to be used by BLI after the LandSense project finishes.
Other impacts	Other organizations have expressed interest in Natura Alert, in particular, the World Conservation Monitoring Centre (WCMC). Talks are ongoing to investigate future collaborations. NaturaAlert has also been integrated into a recent H2020 Green Deal proposal as part of further sustainability efforts. Impact stories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In 2020, SEO/BirdLife made a request to the local and regional authorities of Castilla y León for more clarity and better application of the environmental impact assessments linked to macro farms of pigs, which have proliferated with little control due to the high demand for pig products at national and international level, mainly from China. They have a massive impact on water consumption, pollution of water and soil, and smells. Natura Alert volunteers identified the pig farms as a threat in some key areas for the conservation of birds -

	<p>https://www.europapress.es/sociedad/medio-ambiente-00647/noticia-burbuja-macrogranjas-cerdos-espana-riesgo-acuiferos-areas-protegidas-villafafila-zamora-20171101112926.html</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Volunteers have also highlighted hunting as a threat within the Human intrusions & disturbance category, which aligns with the work carried out by SEO/BirdLife in 2020. As an example, SEO joined forces with other Spanish NGOs to send a letter to the Spanish Environmental Ministry urging them to stop hunting during lockdown https://seo.org/2020/04/20/reclamamos-al-gobierno-de-espana-que-no-permita-la-caza-para-el-control-de-poblaciones-y-que-fomente-medidas-alternativas/ • They also filed a complaint to the High Court of Justice of Asturias against cormorant hunting due to lack of updated population data. The complaint was accepted and hunting stopped - https://seo.org/2020/12/22/suspendido-el-control-de-cormoranes-en-asturias/ • Natura Alert users reported an increasing number of new projects for the deployment of solar power plants and wind farms in which the environmental impact assessments were data deficient, in locations where bird species protected at the national and European level would be greatly affected. In that sense, SEO/BirdLife urged the Andalusian Government to develop a plan for solar power plants in the region to avoid the massive approval of projects without a proper risk assessment on a case by case basis - https://seo.org/2020/12/11/apremiamos-a-la-junta-a-garantizar-que-el-desarrollo-renovable-en-andalucia-no-se-realice-a-costa-de-su-biodiversidad/
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This demonstration case is the most successful of the demonstration cases in LandSense, primarily because of three key elements: (i) the existence of a set of already engaged volunteers in the form of the BirdLife network; (ii) the development of LandSense technology that fills a clear need, i.e., gathering data on threats and operationalization of the IBA threat assessment workflow; and (iii) sustainability beyond the lifetime of LandSense, with upscaling a key part of this future solution. The Change Detection Service (demonstrated in Flores, Indonesia) also represents a successful example of how communities can be engaged to validate alerts (and hence identify threats) as part of a community-based forest monitoring solution. Continuing this work will require additional funding but it represents one area of real potential.

5 Conclusions and Recommendations

This deliverable summarized the demonstration cases that were run within the LandSense project under the main urban dynamics, agricultural and forest habitat monitoring themes. Within the urban dynamics theme, four demonstration cases were described, where the city of Amsterdam represents an upscaling of the technology developed originally for the city of Vienna. The agriculture theme led to the development of the CropSupport service, which was demonstrated as a feasible proof of concept but there are challenges in the engagement of farmers. The two demonstration cases in the forest and habitat monitoring theme demonstrated the use of technology in collecting data on habitat threats, which has filled a gap in the workflows of BirdLife, which has the most potential in terms of sustainability of LandSense technology. In the majority of demonstration cases, local authorities were interested in the solutions, which will lead to some form of sustainability in many of the activities from the project, either as continued development (Natura Alert), new business opportunities (CropSupport), continued investigation into using citizen data for updating authoritative LULC data (IGN), among others.

Based on the feedback received from the different demonstration cases and the evaluation undertaken, the following recommendations can be made regarding future citizen observatory projects:

- Engagement of citizens and sustaining participation is one of the most difficult aspects of any citizen observatory. Where possible, make good use of existing networks such as BirdLife volunteers. Otherwise, a much larger budget should be envisaged for engagement and outreach of citizens in future EU-funded projects that involve citizen observatories.
- Many demonstration cases were undertaken in LandSense, which was driven by the original call text. This approach means that resources are diluted across many efforts and sustaining the efforts across a 4-year project is difficult. Calls that require less demonstration cases would be recommended.
- The Change Detection Service was viewed as having considerable potential as a key component of a citizen observatory. Although there were successful examples demonstrated in the project, more investment is required to produce a service that is capable of detecting a wider range of LULC change types. Such an investment (e.g., through further EU funding) is recommended due to the considerable potential of such a service.
- An analysis of the costs associated with the involvement of citizens in updating authoritative LULC data showed reductions would be possible in one region in France. These types of cost-benefit exercises should be undertaken more frequently within EU projects to demonstrate the real costs associated with the development of a citizen observatory.